

SOX2 Syndrome: A Case with Typical Clinical Profile

UTKARSH BANSAL*, EKANSH RATHORIA**, RAVINDRA AHUJA#, AISHWARYA BAJPAI##, SATVIK JAISWAL•

*Professor and Head, Department of Pediatrics, Hind Institute of Medical Sciences, Safedabad, Barabanki, Uttar Pradesh, India. *utkarsh1003@gmail.com* **Associate Professor, Department of Pediatrics, Hind Institute of Medical Sciences, Safedabad, Barabanki, Uttar Pradesh, India. *rathoriaekansh@yahoo.com* # Professor, Department of Pediatrics, Hind Institute of Medical Sciences, Safedabad, Barabanki, Uttar Pradesh, India. *prof.rahuja@gmail.com* ## Postgraduate, Department of Pediatrics, Hind Institute of Medical Sciences, Safedabad, Barabanki, Uttar Pradesh, India. *aishwaryabajpai92@gmail.com*, •Postgraduate, Department of Pediatrics, Hind Institute of Medical Sciences, Safedabad, Barabanki, Uttar Pradesh, India *dr.jaiswal.21@gmail.com*

ABSTRACT

Anophthalmia (absent eye) or microphthalmia (small eye) is an important cause of severe visual impairment. These developmental eye anomalies may be associated with other phenotypic abnormalities, which should be looked for meticulously in such cases. SOX2 syndrome is the commonest monogenic cause of developmental eye anomalies. The present case is of a six-month-old male who had left-sided anophthalmia, presented with seizures, micropenis, undernutrition and developmental delay.

INTRODUCTION

Anophthalmia is a condition where there is a complete absence of the globe of the eye in the presence of ocular adnexa (eyelids, conjunctiva, and lacrimal apparatus), while microphthalmia refers to a globe with a total axial length that is at least two standard deviations below the mean for age. (1) The prevalence of anophthalmia and microphthalmia is 3 and 14 per 100,000 live births respectively. (2) They may occur in isolation or as part of a syndrome. Usually, these anomalies occur in association with cardiac, musculoskeletal, and/or central nervous system malformations. (3) Anophthalmia/microphthalmia have complex etiology with chromosomal, monogenic, and environmental causes identified. Various chromosomal duplications, deletions, and translocations are implicated. Mutation in the SOX2 gene has been identified as the most common monogenic cause. (4)

CASE HISTORY

A six-month-old male born to a non-consanguineous marriage presented to Paediatrics OPD with complaints of abnormal movements from 1 day. The abnormal movements were generalized, tonic-clonic, multiple episodes lasting for 5-10 minutes, and followed by lethargy. There was a history of similar episodes in the past, starting from 3 months of age, which occurred off and on, and was treated by some local practitioner with phenobarbitone and phenytoin. There was no history of fever, vomiting, loose stools, ear discharge, or head trauma. His bladder & bowel history was normal. There was also a complaint of the absence of left eye from birth, for which no specific management was done in past. The child was born full-term, a cesarean delivery (indicated for meconium-stained liquor) to a 27-year-old mother and 30-year-old father. The mother had taken antenatal care from a local practitioner. According to the mother, her pregnancy was uneventful and she denied having any ultrasonography during pregnancy. There was no history of fever, body rashes, exposure to X-rays, or any significant drug intake during pregnancy. She also took iron supplementation but denied any other medication, smoking, alcohol, or tobacco exposure. There was no family history of anophthalmia/microphthalmia, epilepsy, or malformations. The child had an elder sister 4 years of age, who was healthy. The child was on mixed feeding. He was predominantly given top milk (undiluted cow's milk). Complementary feeding was not started. Family belonged to lower socioeconomic class according to modified Kuppuswamy scale.

CLINICAL EXAMINATION

On examination, he was conscious and oriented. His vital signs were normal. There was a left-sided empty orbit with the presence of eyebrows, eyelids, and eyelashes. The right eye was normal. [Figure 1] The shape of the head was normal. The anterior fontanelle was at a normal level. There was no other obvious dysmorphic facies present. All cranial nerves apart from the left second nerve were intact. The motor and sensory system examinations were normal. The respiratory examination was normal. The abdomen was soft with no signs of organomegaly. Cardiac examination was normal. Back & spine examination showed no abnormality. The genitalia showed bilateral descended testis with a small-sized penis having stretched penile length of 1.5 cm. [Figure 2]

Anthropometric examination revealed weight was 6.1 kg, length was 64 cm, head circumference was 41.5 cm and mid-upper arm circumference was 11.8 cm. According to WHO growth charts the weight-for-age was between 1st and 3rd percentile indicating undernutrition, height-for-age between 3rd and 50th percentile, weight-for-height was between 1st and 3rd percentile indicating moderate acute malnutrition and head circumference-for-age between 3rd and 50th percentile. Ophthalmology reference was done which revealed anophthalmia of the left eye. The ocular size, pupillary reflex, and fundus examination of the right eye were normal. Eye movements were normal on the right side. The head of the child was wobbling on swaying indicating incomplete head control, brought hands together as he played, made cooing sounds, and had a social smile at an observed age of 6 months 10 days (28 weeks). But the child was not able to roll over, sit with support, make a bidextrous grasp or say monosyllables. Thus, there was a global developmental delay with developmental quotient of gross motor, fine motor, social and language milestones being 57.1%, 57.1%, 71.4%, 71.4% respectively with an overall developmental quotient of 64.3%. (6) Development was more retarded in the motor milestones.

FIGURE 1: Left-sided anophthalmia

FIGURE 2: Penile length of 1.5 cm at 6 months of age indicating micropenis (5)

FIGURE 3: CT scan of the head, section at the mid orbital level shows an absence of left eye globe. The rudimentary left optic nerve was also noted. The right eyeball shows mild scleral bulging at the optic disc level.

His investigations were as follows- Hb: 9.6 gm/dL, ESR: 14 mm in 1st hour, WBC: 10200/mm³, N: 64%, L: 32%, E: 1%, M: 1%, Platelet: 470000/mm³. Na: 136.6 meq/L, K: 3.8 meq/L, Ca: 9.3 mg/dL, SGPT: 27 IU/L, SGOT: 24 IU/L, S Creatinine: 0.7 mg/dL. Thyroid Stimulating Hormone: 3.2 μ IU/ml. Chest X-ray and abdominal ultrasound scan were normal. CT scan head was suggestive of the absence of the left eye globe. The rudimentary left optic nerve was also noted. The right eyeball shows mild scleral bulging at the optic disc level. [Figure 3] The brain was normal. The electroencephalogram (EEG) was normal. Parents refused MRI of Brain and Genetic testing because of affordability issue.

The patient was given a sodium valproate loading dose of 20mg/kg and followed by a maintenance dose of 10mg/kg/dose twice a day. Phenobarbitone was stopped and phenytoin was tapered. Seizures were well controlled. Iron supplementation was started and complementary feeding was initiated. Parents were advised to follow up, for growth monitoring, seizure control, and ophthalmologic rehabilitation. They were also advised for molecular genetic testing. The most probable diagnosis of SOX2 syndrome with undernutrition was made as the patient had unilateral anophthalmia, micropenis, seizures, undernutrition, and developmental delay.

DISCUSSION

The SOX2 gene is a member of the sex-determining region of the Y chromosome-related high-mobility group box (SOX) family of transcription factors. (7) Heterozygous mutations in this gene are present in about 10% of cases of anophthalmia/microphthalmia, as its expression is essential for the development of the eye. (8,9,10,11) It also has a role in the development of the forebrain, pituitary, gastrointestinal and urogenital systems. (8,9). It is a rare syndrome with an estimated prevalence of 4 per 1,000,000. (12) SOX2 syndrome was previously described as Anophthalmia-Esophageal-Genital (AEG) syndrome presenting with anophthalmia/microphthalmia, oesophageal atresia with or without tracheo-oesophageal fistula, and urogenital anomalies (most commonly cryptorchidism, hypospadias and micropenis) by Rogers (13) and named by Shah et al. (14). The term Microphthalmia-anophthalmia-coloboma (MAC) spectrum was also used to in the past (1), but as a wide phenotypic spectrum was described over the period of time these nomenclature have lost significance. Up to the mid of 2020, 174 individuals from 157 families had been identified with SOX2 syndrome across the world. (4)

High suspicion of SOX2 syndrome should be kept with the following: (4)

• CLINICAL FINDINGS

- Bilateral anophthalmia and/or microphthalmia
- Unilateral anophthalmia or microphthalmia
- Genital abnormalities. Frequently cryptorchidism and/or a micropenis in males (commonly a manifestation of hypogonadotropic hypogonadism); infrequently uterus hypoplasia and ovary or vaginal agenesis in females
- Seizures
- Spasticity, dystonia, or status dystonicus
- Delayed motor development/learning disability
- Postnatal growth failure
- Tracheoesophageal fistula and/or esophageal atresia
- Brain MRI. Malformation and/or gray matter heterotopia of the mesial temporal structures (hippocampal and parahippocampal), pituitary hypoplasia, and agenesis or dysgenesis of the corpus callosum.
- Family history of autosomal dominant inheritance, including simplex cases (i.e., a single occurrence in a family). But the absence of a known family history does not exclude the diagnosis. In certain cases, one parent possesses the mutated gene only in their gametes which the offspring inherits. (germline mosaicism)

DIAGNOSIS: It is established by molecular genetic testing in a proband (affected individual through whom a family with a genetic disorder is ascertained). It could be a heterozygous intragenic SOX2 pathogenic variant or an intragenic deletion or a deletion of 3q26.33 involving SOX2. (4)

RECOMMENDED EVALUATIONS (4):

- Anthropometric assessment for growth failure
- Complete ophthalmologic examination
- Hearing assessment
- Neurologic examination for hypotonia, dystonia
- Genitourinary examination for penile length and cryptorchidism in males
- Ultrasound for ovarian and uterine anomalies in females
- Endocrine evaluation for growth hormone, thyroid hormone, and gonadotrophins
- Developmental assessment for intellectual disability
- Cranial MRI for brain or pituitary malformations, optic nerve evaluation, and mesial temporal heterotopia (associated with epilepsy)
- EEG for seizures

MANAGEMENT: depends on the manifestations and may require a multidisciplinary approach (4):

- Pediatric ophthalmology: best-corrected visual acuity in microphthalmia and prostheses in anophthalmia
- Pediatric Neurology: Anti-epileptic treatment
- Pediatric endocrinology: Hormone replacement therapy
- Otolaryngology: Hearing aids

- Physiotherapy/Occupational Therapy
- Urology: cryptorchidism or other genital malformations
- Surgery: Esophageal atresia or tracheoesophageal fistula
- Early Intervention Program

RISK IN FAMILY MEMBERS OF A PROBAND (4):

- Siblings: If a parent is affected and/or has the genetic alteration identified in the proband, the risk to the siblings is 50%. Even if genetic alteration cannot be detected in either parent, the recurrence risk to siblings is greater than that of the general population because of the possibility of parental germline mosaicism.
- Offspring: In a female proband the risk to the offspring is 50%, but in a male proband it has not been reported.
- Preconception genetic counselling and fetal anomaly morphology scan/fetal MRI (15) in the 2nd trimester is recommended for siblings and other family members at risk.

CONCLUSION

A case of anophthalmia/microphthalmia could be a part of a syndrome and/or maybe associated with other systemic malformation. Such cases should be diligently examined and investigated. In our case, the diagnosis of SOX2 syndrome was made on the clinical findings as molecular testing could not be done for confirmation. SOX2 syndrome requires a multidisciplinary management approach and follow-up.

CORRESPONDING AUTHOR

DR UTKARSH BANSAL
Professor & Head, Department of Pediatrics, Hind Institute of Medical Sciences,
Safedabad, Barabanki, Uttar Pradesh, India
email : utkarsh1003@gmail.com

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REFERENCES

1. **Bardakjian T, Weiss A, Schneider A.** Microphthalmia/Anophthalmia/Coloboma Spectrum – Retired Chapter, For Historical Reference Only. 2004 Jan 29 [updated 2015 Jul 9]. In: Adam MP, Ardinger HH, Pagon RA, et al., editors. GeneReviews® [Internet]. Seattle (WA): University of Washington, Seattle; 1993–2021. Available from: <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/20301552/>
2. **Morrison D, FitzPatrick D, Hanson I, Williamson K, van Heyningen V, Fleck B, Jones I, Chalmers J, Campbell H.** National study of microphthalmia, anophthalmia, and coloboma (MAC) in Scotland: investigation of genetic aetiology. *J Med Genet.* 2002;39:16–22. doi: 10.1136/jmg.39.1.16.
3. **Verma AS, Fitzpatrick DR.** Anophthalmia and microphthalmia. *Orphanet J Rare Dis.* 2007;2:47.
4. **Williamson KA, Yates TM, FitzPatrick DR.** SOX2 Disorder. 2006 Feb 23 [Updated 2020 Jul 30]. In: Adam MP, Ardinger HH, Pagon RA, et al., editors. GeneReviews® [Internet]. Seattle (WA): University of Washington, Seattle; 1993–2021. Available from: <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/books/NBK1300/>
5. **Jaiswal VK, Khadilkar V, Khadilkar A, Lohiya N.** Stretched penile length and testicular size from birth to 18 years in boys from Western Maharashtra. *Indian J Endocr Metab* 2019;23:3-8
6. **Illingworth RS. Normal Development.** In: Development of the infant and the young child. Nair M, Russell P, editors. Elsevier Health Sciences Apac; 2013.
7. **Stevanovic M, Zuffardi O, Collignon J, Lovell-Badge R, Goodfellow P.** The cDNA sequence and chromosomal location of the human SOX2 gene. *Mamm Genome* 1994; 5: 640–642.
8. **Fantes J, Ragge NK, Lynch SA et al:** Mutations in SOX2 cause anophthalmia. *Nat Genet* 2003; 33: 461–463.
9. **Ragge NK, Lorenz B, Schneider A, Bushby K, de Sanctis L, de Sanctis U et al:** SOX2 anophthalmia syndrome. *Am J Med Genet A* 2005; 135: 1–7; discussion 8.
10. **Bakrania P, Robinson DO, Bunyan DJ et al:** SOX2 anophthalmia syndrome: 12 new cases demonstrating broader phenotype and high frequency of large gene deletions. *Br J Ophthalmol* 2007; 91: 1471–1476.
11. **Schneider A, Bardakjian T, Reis LM, Tyler RC, Semina EV.** Novel SOX2 mutations and genotype-phenotype correlation in anophthalmia and microphthalmia. *Am J Med Genet A* 2009; 149A: 2706–2715.
12. **Shah SP, Taylor AE, Sowden JC, Ragge NK, Russell-Eggitt I, Rahi JS, et al.** Anophthalmos, microphthalmos, and typical coloboma in the United Kingdom: a prospective study of incidence and risk. *Invest Ophthalmol Vis Sci.* 2011;52:558–64.
13. **Rogers RC.** Unknown cases. *Proc Greenwood Genet Center.* 1988; 7,57.
14. **Shah D, Jones R, Porter H, Turnpenny P.** Bilateral microphthalmia, esophageal atresia, and cryptorchidism: the anophthalmia-esophageal-genital syndrome. *Am J Med Genet.* 1997;70(2):171-3.
15. **Searle A, Shetty P, Melov SJ, Alahakoon TI.** Prenatal diagnosis and implications of microphthalmia and anophthalmia with a review of current ultrasound guidelines: two case reports. *J Med Case Rep.* 2018;12(1):250.